

PSM and AI

Part 1:

Mapping how public service
media use AI in journalism

July 2025

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1. Introduction

Accuracy, accountability, impartiality, universal access, and editorial independence. These are some of the core values that drive public service media (PSM) and their mandate to serve the public interest and support democratic discourse through high quality, trusted news content. But in a world where PSM face increasingly difficult financial and political conditions, and amid an increasingly threatening environment for journalists, how best can PSM newsrooms source, create and distribute content without risking the values they hold dear?

Some say that Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds the key. The rapid advancement of AI has transformed the global media landscape, raising fundamental questions about the role of technology in democratic life. Nowhere are these questions more acute than PSM, where it is crucial to assess how these technologies can aid their mission without endangering public trust.

AI has the potential to enhance the function of PSM. AI tools offer opportunities to streamline production processes, personalise content delivery, automate mundane tasks, and improve accessibility through tools like speech-to-text, translation, and captioning. These capabilities can help PSM reach wider and more diverse audiences, improve efficiency amid budget constraints, and respond more rapidly to breaking news or dis- and misinformation.

However, AI also presents profound risks that go to the heart of PSM's legitimacy. Tools powered by opaque algorithms and proprietary datasets raise serious concerns about transparency and accountability—principles essential to trust. Algorithmic bias, "hallucinations", where a programme spits out false or nonsensical text, and the exclusionary dynamics of commercial data infrastructure can threaten the public service values PSM are expected to uphold. Financial and technological feasibility means that many smaller PSM rely on third-party vendors, with potential risks to editorial independence and technological sovereignty.

These tensions have led to calls for a more collective and values-driven approach to innovation within the PSM sector. Efforts by the Director General 8 group (DG8), the European Broadcasting Union (EBU), the Public Media

Alliance (PMA) and other associations reflects a growing consensus that shared standards, and collaborative frameworks, are needed to guide the ethical and sustainable use of AI.

Yet, despite these policy-level discussions, there remains a significant empirical gap in our understanding of how PSM actually use AI in practice. Most existing research is either limited to Western Europe or is narrowly focused on recommender systems. This limits the ability of researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to assess the impact of AI on the editorial work of public service newsrooms or to identify best practices and areas of concern across different regions and media systems.

To address this gap, Professor Kate Wright (University of Edinburgh) has conducted the first broadly-based international study of PSMs' approaches to responsible AI within journalism production. The study, which was designed in collaboration with the Public Media Alliance, draws on survey data, internal documents, and interviews with senior managers and stakeholders across thirteen public media organisations from Africa, Asia, the Caribbean, Europe, and Oceania. It was funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) as part of the Bridging Responsible AI Divides scheme.

To disseminate the results of this research project and stimulate further discussion, Kate Wright and the CEO of Public Media Alliance (PMA), Kristian Porter, have authored two industry reports. This is the first. It maps PSMs' current use of AI in journalism production: exploring which AI tools PSM use, how they use them, and how senior managers frame and justify their use in relation to PSM values. While the second will explore PSMs' organisational policies, the responsibilities of PSM in relation to AI, and the dilemmas they face regarding AI procurement.

It is hoped these reports will contribute to an urgently needed body of knowledge about the evolving role of AI in public service media, providing a foundation for more informed, collective discussion within the industry about how to harness technological innovation in a way that strengthens—rather than compromises—the democratic mission of PSM.

2. Methods

2.1 Defining 'AI' and 'Public Service Media'

In this study, Artificial Intelligence is defined broadly as **"a collection of ideas, technologies¹, and techniques that relate to a computer system's capacity to ... perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence."** So, AI encompasses, but is not confined to, generative AI (GenAI); embracing various forms of automation, machine learning, and data analysis.

Participants were asked about their use of AI in the production of 'journalism' rather than 'news.' This was because PSMs tend to 'draw the line' differently. Some distinguish between the uses of AI permitted in hard news and other content, while others differentiate between factual and other content. By asking about 'journalism', we were also able to address a range of other genres, including current affairs and investigative documentaries,

which have not previously been analysed in other studies.

PSM tend to be defined in terms of their commitment to public service values. But it is difficult to define a sample of organisations in this way, as some organisations that self-describe as PSM are state-controlled; while others move back and forth between degrees of government control over time and in response to political events. For this reason, we approached a diverse range of organisations able to exercise significant editorial independence, based on the latest version of the global State Media Monitor², as well as PMA's professional judgement. Full details are available in the academic article on which this report is based, which is undergoing peer review as of August 2025.

2.2 Data and Sample

13 organisations participated in this study, as listed in Table 1 (page 6). These media networks operate across five continents, work in a range of languages, and serve a mixture of domestic and international audiences. Unfortunately, we were unable to include any networks from North America as they declined, owing to the operational demands relating to general elections in the USA and Canada in 2024 and 2025 respectively.

Given the importance of resourcing, organisations are listed in order of annual income: with high-annual income being classed as €500M+p/a; medium-income as €100M+ p/a; and low-income as less than €100M p/a.

We originally intended to have five organisations per category, but two high-income organisations were unable to proceed. Our sample therefore contains more organisations with medium and low incomes, but this is more representative of the sector.

The data on which this report is based included an online survey, which all participating organisations returned, and semi-structured interviews with designated senior managers

provided by 10 organisations.

Data collection took place between May and December 2024, so this report can be treated as a 'baseline study' conducted before the release of open-source models by the Chinese firm DeepSeek, and the very rapid industry and political changes which took place in the USA at the start of the second Trump administration.

This data collection period was longer than we had originally intended because AI was almost universally regarded as highly sensitive by PSM, which slowed down the process of obtaining organisational consent. But this longer data collection period had some advantages: enabling participants to attend various meetings between PSMs about AI³, and to reflect on the relationship of AI to political change, as 2024 was a 'mega-election' year in which voters in more than 60 countries went to the polls⁴. We will now go on to discuss our findings, beginning with an overview of the 'state of play.'

¹ reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/our-research/industry-led-debate-how-uk-media-cover-artificial-intelligence

² statemediamonitor.com

Table 1: List of participating organisations

Name	Acronym	Country	Income Category	Annual Income
Nippon Hōsō Kyōkai* (trans: Japan Broadcasting)	NHK	Japan	High	€4.3 billion (2023)
Swiss Broadcasting Corporation	SRG SSR	Switzerland	High	€1.6 billion (2022–3)
Australian Broadcasting Corporation	ABC	Australia	High	Combined government/ commercial income €741 million (2022–3)
Radio-télévision belge de la Communauté française (trans: Belgian Radio-television of the French Community)	RTBF	Belgium (French)	Medium	€469 million (2023)
Vlaamse Radio- en- Televisieomroeporganisatie (trans: Flemish Radio and Broadcasting Organisation)	VRT	Belgium (Flemish)	Medium	€465.4 million
Special Broadcasting Service	SBS	Australia	Medium	€307.1 million
Sveriges Radio (trans: Swedish Radio)	SR	Sweden	Medium	€290.6 million (2022–3)
South Africa Broadcasting Corporation	SABC	South Africa	Medium	€241.4 million (2023)
Public Television Service	PTS	Taiwan	Low	€71.7 million (2022)
Suspilne (trans: Public) Prior to 2022 known as National Public Broadcasting Company of Ukraine	-	Ukraine	Low	€40.5 million (2023)
Radio New Zealand	RNZ	New Zealand	Low	€32.3 million (2022–3)
Public Broadcasting Corporation of Jamaica	PBCJ	Jamaica	Low	€8.8 million (2023–4)
TeleRadio Moldova	TRM	Moldova	Low	€8.3 million (2023)

³ Such as the meetings held by the Asia-Pacific Broadcasting Union, Médias Francophones Publiques, Public Television System, and the South Africa Broadcasting Corporation.

⁴ pewresearch.org/global/2024/12/11/global-elections-in-2024-what-we-learned-in-a-year-of-political-disruption

3. Overview

3.1 How long have PSM used AI to inform or assist journalism production?

10 of the 13 organisations in this study said they used AI to assist or inform their journalism production.

The amount of time which participants said they had used AI for is illustrated in Figure 1.

To clarify, five organisations said that they had only used AI for 1-2 years. These were: ABC (Australia) PTS (Taiwan), SBS (Australia), Suspilne (Ukraine), and the Flemish-Belgian network, VRT.

Four had used AI for between 2-5 years. These were: the Francophone-Belgian network, RTBF (2-3 years); RNZ (New Zealand) and SR (Sweden) (3-4 years); and SRG SSR (Switzerland) (4-5 years).

NHK (Japan) appeared to be the most experienced: it stated that it had used AI tools for 8+ years. NHK has a longstanding inhouse R&D team, which publishes its own research papers online⁵.

The three organisations that stated they did not use AI were PBCJ (Jamaica), SABC (South Africa), and TRM (Moldova). However, in their research interviews, PBCJ and TRM participants clarified this: saying that their journalists did use AI tools, but not in an 'official' capacity.

These participants and specialised trainers said that journalists who used AI 'unofficially' tended to use free versions of Otter.AI (for transcription); DeepL and GoogleTranslate (for translation) and OpenAI's ChatGPT (for research).

SABC did not choose to do a follow-up interview, but previous academic research suggests that some of their journalists use AI 'unofficially' for translation⁶.

Journalists' unauthorised use of such AI tools was widely seen by senior managers and specialist trainers as posing significant risks regarding cybersecurity and data privacy. Yet the decision to adopt and regulate AI tools internally was not straightforward.

For instance, TRM (Moldova) explained that the network's income was so low that very few options were available to them, apart from using budget tools offered by or developed in China, which senior managers regarded as a step too far—even before the launch of open-source tools by DeepSeek in Jan 2025⁷.

While PBCJ (Jamaica) was concerned that formally adopting AI tools not only raised questions about affordability, but also the potential to become a target for cybercrime. In addition, adopting AI tools would require board and government approval, which risked politicisation.

Figure 1: Duration of AI use as stated by survey respondents

⁵ nhk.or.jp/str/english

⁶ https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17512786.2021.1984976?casa_token=fFdV96BjxMQAAAAA%3AgKHrgnNB6LclPd0fUxDR4lbwysyBkXJ7m8ZX2dZn2rbao4ge6dY7Mr0PAvLz8iqf10ss03SMfTYDDoA

⁷ tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/21670811.2025.2502129?src=exp-la#d1e451

3.2. How important is organisational income for PSM in developing AI strategies?

PSM with higher organisational incomes tended to have used AI for longer, with one exception: ABC (Australia) had taken a slower, more cautious approach to adopting AI than other high-income organisations.

Despite the high cost of developing AI and embedding it successfully in journalists' routines, AI innovation was not the sole preserve of high-income PSM.

In-house tools had been developed by some medium- and one low-income PSM in a comparatively short time. One medium income PSM, SR (Sweden), was consistently described as having become a leader in AI innovation by other participants.

However, organisations that did have an AI strategy in place at the time of interviewing tended to have lower incomes. SABC (South Africa) is positioned at the bottom of the medium-income bracket, while PBCJ (Jamaica) and TRM (Moldova) were at the bottom of the low-income category.

PSM with lower incomes said they struggled to afford AI applications that they believed to be secure and could not afford to employ AI specialists to assess or develop such tools. Low staffing levels meant that finding the 'bandwidth' to consider how to approach AI was also challenging. As a PBCJ executive put it, **"We don't even have the resources to think about AI ... what is happening globally, how it will affect us and [how] to brace for that effect."**

3.3. How Eurocentric is the conversation about PSM and AI?

The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) continues to operate as the most significant hub for collective dialogue and productisation (product development) between PSM. Suspilne (Ukraine), expressed particular appreciation for their inclusion in EBU's European Perspective project⁸.

However, European PSM did not seem to benefit equally. Another low-income PSM, TRM (Moldova), which is also experiencing acute tensions with Russia⁹, voiced frustration with other comparatively wealthy European PSM. A representative said:

"We have had a very nice conversation with [A senior BBC executive] and he told me, 'Well, even for the BBC, money is a problem.' ... The [senior executive] at Deutsche Welle also told me once that they have budget cuts every year, and they have to adapt and adjust.

When I look at ... the figures [in both organisations], even in the context of budget cuts, I still think that it is easier to cut a big cake than to cut nothing.

I don't really think that they get us ... It is one thing to try and [hire AI experts at large PSM] which have a name and proper resources. It's a completely different thing to hire at TRM, where the building was supposed

to be demolished 20 years ago and the wind is whistling through the windows, and salaries are low."

By contrast, high-income PSM outside Europe had relatively easy access to peers via formal networks. For example ABC (Australia) and NHK-Japan are members of the Director General 8 (DG8). ABC also reported finding EBU conferences and other sessions "super useful," as well as engaging in more informal "catch ups" online with EBU, the BBC R&D team, and Nordic PSM. But there was still a reluctance to share Intellectual Property, as one senior manager put it:

"There are a lot of organisational similarities, I think, so it's fairly easy to knock on doors and get a conversation going ... Of course, it's usually bilateral conversations or occasionally, multilateral conversations...

It's very much... a sense of 'well, what are you up to and can we learn from you?' or "What are your ideas?", that sort of thing.

But ... none of that is productised; you can't exactly hand code over ... or [say] 'Can we have your code please?' because none of us are at that level, that I'm aware of."

Further regional conversations appear to take place between ABC (Australia) and others in Oceania, including RNZ (New Zealand). This helped offset the difficulties that other PSM in the region faced in funding the long-haul travel necessary to attend conferences outside the region.

While PSM outside Europe were aware of the risk of discussions about PSM and AI becoming too Eurocentric, other regional hubs did not seem to operate as comparable hubs to the EBU. Sometimes there weren't enough PSM to form a 'critical mass' and, sometimes, broadcasting unions and other regional organisations do not impose a definition of PSM on their members, which led to state-controlled media attending sessions on PSM and AI. In such contexts, PSM senior managers and trainers said they did not feel comfortable sharing much detail about their experiences or pilot projects.

The lack of comparable regional hubs for dialogue between PSM seems likely to be a particular problem for PSM with lower organisational incomes, as they did not appear to participate in regular, informal, online conversations with other PSM, even though some faced serious internal and external threats.

For example, a PBCJ (Jamaica) said they were aware of online conversations in Europe, as well as PMA's international workshops, but low staffing levels meant they struggled to find time to participate or keep up with other coverage of AI. However, one organisation, PTS Taiwan, chose to deal with this issue by hosting one of their annual symposia on 'The Challenges and Opportunities Facing PSM in the Age of AI', in conjunction with PMA in autumn 2024¹⁰.

Questions for further discussion:

- Given that most PSM in this study are relatively new to AI, how can PMA and other multilateral associations best assist and support them?
- Do PSMs with more experience of AI have any normative obligations to help, work with, or simply listen to other PSM, especially those with lower incomes and those facing serious democratic threats?
- What kinds of regional and cross-regional networks might be appropriate, useful, and sustainable for PSM, PMA, and other supporting organisations?
- How should "PSM" be defined to foster fruitful collective discussions about responsible AI?

⁸ europeanperspective.net/home

⁹ apnews.com/article/moldova-democracy-election-russia-disinformation-corruption-0a23e330da7121dbc34b085fc5d0d8ad

¹⁰ publicmediaalliance.org/how-can-ai-bolster-psm-mission

4. PSM and AI tools

4.1. What AI tools are PSM using?

The 10 PSM which said they used AI to inform or support journalism were asked to name up to five tools, how they used them, and how they sourced them. In all, they named 42 tools, none of which dominated the sample (see Appendix for full dataset).

These tools were used for a variety of purposes. The most popular was transcription, which was mentioned by all participants. The second most popular was image generation and editing, which were mentioned by half of the sample.

Fewer participants mentioned AI-enabled translation, AI presenters, synthetic voice technology, and other activities relating to journalistic research, including image verification and facial recognition technology. However, the fastest growing use of AI involved repurposing news content for online services and social media platforms.

Most uses did not differ significantly from those reported in the global JournalismAI project¹¹, which included a small number of PSM alongside many other news organisations.

In addition, most of the tools that PSMs used did not seem especially distinctive. Only eight of the tools used 'officially' by PSM (19% of the sample) were developed in-house, and only one tool (2%) was developed in collaboration with other PSM, via EBU.

As Diagram 2 shows, the majority of AI tools were provided externally by commercial companies (27 tools, 64% of the sample)¹².

Diagram 2: AI tool provenance

¹¹ lse.ac.uk/media-and-communications/polis/JournalismAI

¹² We will reflect on the implications of PSMs' use of commercial AI providers in our second report on the Responsible Procurement of AI.

4.2. How much did PSM depend on the 'Big Five' technology companies?

Although we can only report what participants told us, the 'Big Five' technology companies (Google, Apple, Facebook/Meta, Amazon and Microsoft) seemed to be less dominant than expected. Google and Microsoft supplied a total of three tools, cited by one participant each (Microsoft Github Copilot, Google Pinpoint and Google Reverse Image Search). Although Amazon and Microsoft products (e.g. AWSBedrock, AWSTranscribe, Microsoft Bing) underpinned a further five hybrid tools.

So, the 'Big Five' either supplied or contributed to 19% of the tools 'officially' used by PSM, and these were deployed by 38% of study participants. However, these companies also appeared to provide other forms of infrastructure to PSM, analysis of which was outside the scope of this project. For example, Suspilne (Ukraine) decided to host its website on Google Cloud for security reasons, shortly after the Russian invasion.

By contrast, other commercial companies supplied or contributed to 24 tools (57% of the sample), and 53% of participants relied upon them.

The most commonly cited was Adobe (six participants referred to Firefly or Photoshop) and OpenAI (three participants cited ChatGPT, CustomGPT, Dall-E). OpenAI products (ChatGPT and Whisper) also underpinned a further two hybrid tools. PSM should be aware that OpenAI has been sued for training its tools using copyrighted material, scraped from the web¹³, and that its move to become a for-profit company is highly contested¹⁴.

As the database of AI tools in the Appendix shows, a wide variety of commercial companies were mentioned (17 in total¹⁵, although the companies producing two other tools could not be traced¹⁶.) Common and emerging uses of AI will now be discussed in relation to specific tools.

¹³ nytimes.com/2023/12/27/business/media/new-york-times-open-ai-microsoft-lawsuit.html

¹⁴ vox.com/future-perfect/380117/openai-microsoft-sam-altman-nonprofit-for-profit-foundation-artificial-intelligence

¹⁵ These were: Adobe, Anthropic, Canva, Chartbeat, cSubtitle, ElevenLabs, EMEARobotics, GoodTape, Grammarly, GrayLark Technologies, Midjourney, OpenAI, OtterAI, Sysran, Talkwalker, Trint, Wobby.

¹⁶ These were both Russian facial recognition technology tools, discussed in the final findings section: Findclone and Search4Faces.

5. Speech-to-text tools

5.1. Transcription and captions

The most popular use of AI cited by PSM was speech-to-text transcription, which was mentioned by all 10 participants whose organisations used AI 'officially.'

Transcription had multiple uses in journalism production. It aided conversations between journalists and news managers, especially within multilingual organisations, and facilitated journalistic research. AI-enabled transcription also helped to repurpose news content rapidly. For example, journalists often produced automated transcripts to help them convert broadcast interviews into shorter online articles.

Speech-to-text tools were also used in public-facing contexts to meet PSMs' universal accessibility obligations by providing hearing-impaired audiences with full transcripts of podcasts and/or producing captions for TV and video.

5.2. Speech-to-text tools and data privacy

Data privacy, as well as universal access, also informed SR's approach to the development of in-house speech-to-text tools. As a network executive said, "If we [used] external AI services, we can't guarantee that they're not training on our content—and we don't want them to do that."

Other organisations used transcription tools provided by various commercial companies, including Sonix¹⁸, and a paid-for version of OtterAI. But some were becoming uncomfortable with this and were looking for alternatives. For example, one senior manager who preferred to remain anonymous in this context, explained:

"Everyone at [our network] is concerned about where our information is going because we just don't know. We did register with Otter.AI for transcription..."

However, only 3 PSM said they currently used in-house models for AI transcription, all of which were high-or medium-income organisations. These were: ABC (Australia), NHK (Japan), and SR (Sweden). A fourth organisation, which chose to remain anonymous in this context, said transcription was one of the functions of its hybrid AI system.

It is worth noting here that although SR (Sweden) is a medium-income organisation, it appeared to have done some of the most extensive development of in-house speech-to-text tools for universal access¹⁷. It provided in-house transcription for podcasts and other programming, and was rolling out AI-enabled captions for its app during winter 2024. SR had also developed an in-house sound optimisation tool to aid in-car listening for the hearing-impaired.

[But] people who had their own accounts on their laptops [found that] every time they entered a meeting, it would say, 'John's AI' and then it would randomly record stuff.

It made people really nervous that they had signed up for a transcription tool, but all of a sudden their meetings were being weirdly recorded ... it was quite alarming."

In a follow-up conversation with another PSM in (northern) spring 2025, a senior manager at ABC (Australia) confirmed that the network had banned its staff from using Otter.AI, as it had failed all of ABC's data privacy and security assessments.

Some PSM chose to address concerns about data privacy by using GDPR-compliant providers (e.g., GoodTape¹⁹ and Trint²⁰), even when they were based outside Europe.

5.3. Translation

Accurate transcription was widely seen as the precursor of AI-enabled translation. This interested PSM because of their commitment to diversity, but was of particular interest to multilingual PSM, as manual translation is expensive and takes so much time. Only three organisations mentioned that they currently use AI to aid translation. These were: NHK (Japan), SR (Sweden) and SRG SSR (Switzerland).

The international arm of NHK (NHK World-Japan) appeared to use it most extensively, deploying an in-house tool to livestream news with English subtitles, automatically translated into nine other languages, and to provide online articles and Video-on-Demand in nineteen languages.

However, the 'unofficial' use of AI translation tools could prove deeply problematic, especially when published without checking. A striking example was given by a senior manager at TRM (Moldova), who said that one of the network's journalists had used an unauthorised AI tool to translate material about a sensitive court case for the Russian language section of the network's website.

The TRM journalist, who was on an overnight shift, had not properly proofread the article before publication. As a result, the network falsely reported that the court had "beheaded" the defendant, causing what the senior manager described as a "huge scandal" the following morning.

5.4. Variable accuracy of speech-to-text tools and minority or Indigenous languages

The most common challenge mentioned by PSM in relation to speech-to-text tools was their accuracy could vary dramatically. English and Chinese Mandarin transcriptions were consistently identified as the most accurate because AI tools were trained using large corpora scraped from online sources.

However, interviewees said AI tools still struggled to transcribe some English accents and dialects, such as New Zealand English. PTS (Taiwan) had also opted to use a Hong-Kong based specialist, cSubtitle²¹ (despite considerable tensions with China), because other AI transcription services could not differentiate sufficiently between Chinese Mandarin, Taiwanese Mandarin, and Hong Kong Cantonese.

¹⁷ thefix.media/2024/9/23/what-can-newsrooms-learn-from-swedish-radio-ai-strategy

¹⁸ sonix.ai

¹⁹ goodtape.io

²⁰ trint.com

²¹ csubtitle.com

Romansch

PSM working in minority languages experienced even lower rates of transcription accuracy because of the lack of readily available training data online. But building training corpora is an expensive, highly-skilled, and time-consuming task. SRG SSR (Switzerland) addressed this problem by commissioning a commercial start-up launched by a university to construct a corpus of Romansch²², a language spoken by fewer than 10,000 people in the Grisons canton, with five different idioms.

Hakka

However, this was not an option for low-income PSM, which tended to feed into government-funded projects run by non-commercial actors instead. For example, PTS (Taiwan) contributed archival material to an academic corpus-construction project supported by the government's Hakka Affairs Council. Hakka, with its five dialects, is spoken by 15-20% of Taiwan's population and is considered to be endangered²³. The corpus, which was published in March 2024, took two years to build²⁴. At the time of writing in (northern) spring 2025, PTS was collaborating with Taiwanese academics to use the corpus to develop live captioning for Hakka TV²⁵.

Māori

Developing Indigenous languages corpora was widely regarded as the most difficult task of all: compounding the challenges of minority languages with concerns about Indigenous data sovereignty²⁶. For this reason, Māori non-profit, Te Hiku Media²⁷, secured funding from the New Zealand government to support its crowdsourcing of a Māori corpus and use it to train speech-to-text and text-to-speech tools in a project known as Papa Reo²⁸. Beginning in 2020, by 2024 Te Hiku Media had produced remarkably accurate tools²⁹. This is particularly impressive since New Zealand speakers often "code-switch": incorporating words from Te Reo Māori (the Māori language) and New Zealand English within a single utterance, creating additional technical challenges.

Like PTS in Taiwan, RNZ (New Zealand) contributed decades of archival material to the Māori corpus. In return, the network will be permitted to use the tools produced by Te Hiku Media for transcription and on-screen captioning. The RNZ interviewee also said they hoped that RNZ's use of tools provided by Te Hiku Media would avoid perpetuating harmful historical biases within the network's archival metadata. However, RNZ's approach means that any other future translation tools the network uses (for example, to translate Mandarin Chinese), will have to be designed to be compatible with those provided by Te Hiku Media.

²² sator.com/automated-romansh-translation-now-available-for-the-first-time/#:~:text=Now%2C%20for%20the%20first%20time%2C%20it%20is%20possible%20to%20use,translation%20for%20the%20Romansh%20language

²³ ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10482979

²⁴ hakatv.org.tw/news-detail/1709288985235265

²⁵ hakatv.org.tw/news-detail/1679632232246710

²⁶ gida-global.org

²⁷ tehiku.nz

²⁸ papareo.nz

²⁹ rnz.co.nz/news/te-manu-korihia/527405/maori-media-company-head-peter-lucas-jones-named-on-time-magazine-list-for-preserving-te-reo-through-ai

5.5. Challenging cases: Jamaica and South Africa

Two of the PSM most interested in developing AI translation in future were PBCJ (Jamaica) and SABC (South Africa). But both are likely to face pronounced technical challenges. Jamaican Patois or Patwa has a distinct grammar, syntax and vocabulary—drawing words from African, European and Asian languages³⁰. Like most oral languages, Patois is spoken differently across the country, so there is no "gold standard" to measure accurate transcription against, let alone translation.

SABC is committed to providing programming in all of South Africa's official languages³¹, several of which are Indigenous³². "Code-switching" is common in South Africa: that is, when a speaker uses words from multiple languages in the same utterance. In addition, some languages like Xhosa are primarily oral, so are spoken differently across the country³³. These compounded by the imposition of writing by colonial-era missionaries in ways that often bore little resemblance to how languages were actually spoken.

Accurate AI transcription and translation continues to be a significant challenge for many PSM. Some of those facing the greatest technical challenges also have low organisational incomes.

Questions for further discussion:

- Might PSMs, which have developed their own transcription and translation tools, be willing to share some of what they have learned with others thinking of moving in this direction?
- What are the pros and cons of using transcription tools from large companies without strong regulatory mechanisms versus using smaller, GDPR-compliant providers?
- What are the pros and cons of contributing to government-funded corpus-construction projects in partnership with universities or non-profits? Might those with experience of these projects be willing to share their experiences?
- Is there scope for a working group or informal network of PSM working on virtual sign-readers?
- How could PMA and other associations best support PSM coping with challenges regarding the transcription and translation of minority and Indigenous languages, especially organisations with lower incomes? For example, might it be useful to collate a list of academic experts skilled in developing minority language corpora, or facilitate collaboration between PSM with overlapping minority populations?

³⁰ nytimes.com/2023/10/11/world/americas/jamaica-official-language-patois.html

³¹ web.sabc.co.za/digital/stage/editorialpolicies/Policies/SABC-Editorial-Policy-LANGUAGE.pdf

³² These are: Afrikaans, English, Ndebele, Northern Sotho, Southern Sotho, Tsonga, Tswana, Swati, Venda, Xhosa and Zulu. Sign language was added in 2023.

³³ isca-archive.org/sigul_2023/markl23_sigul.html

6. Images, AI presenters, and Synthetic Voices

6.1. Image generation and editing

The second most cited area of current AI use was image generation and editing. This was mentioned by seven participants: ABC (Australia), PTS (Taiwan), RNZ (New Zealand), RTBF (Francophone-Belgium) and VRT (Flemish-Belgium), SRG SSR (Switzerland), and Suspilne (Ukraine).

AI-enabled tools rapidly improved the efficiency of editing images required in high volumes for online publishing. However, AI-generated images were generally graphics and non-realistic illustrations used to “promote” other journalistic content on social media. So, AI-enabled image generation and editing both seem to have emerged in response to the longstanding pressure to repurpose content and compete for audiences’ attention on multiple online and social media platforms.

Most PSMs used Adobe’s Firefly and Photoshop tools for image generation and editing. PSMs’ choice of these tools was influenced by familiarity and ease of access because, as one interviewee said, these products were already “on their desktop” via organisational subscriptions to Adobe’s Creative Cloud.

Organisations also mentioned commitments made by Adobe and another commercial provider, Canva, to avoid training their tools using customer-created content. However, two PSMs said they used Midjourney, which has been sued in the United States for breach of copyright³⁴. The case is complex, ongoing and no final judgement had been reached at the time of writing.

³⁴ reuters.com/legal/litigation/ai-companies-lose-bid-dismiss-parts-visual-artists-copyright-case-2024-08-13

6.2. AI Presenters and Sign-readers

The most serious ethical concerns raised by PSM senior managers involved the use of AI tools to create human-seeming synthetic ‘presenters’, which are becoming common in parts of Asia and the Middle East³⁵, following the introduction of AI news anchors by China’s wire agency, Xinhua, in 2018. Most participants argued that AI presenters would not be accepted by PSM audiences, who might view them as deceptive, which risked damaging public trust in their journalism.

In addition, participants were profoundly concerned about playing into the hands of malicious actors who already create ‘deepfakes’ of their content to spread mis- and disinformation. As an ABC interviewee (Australia) explained, if

“...someone else makes up an avatar and fakes ABC News, you [would be] in much more difficult territory saying, ‘Oh no, no, that fake person that has been created is the wrong ABC avatar. This is the real ABC avatar’.

AI anchors seem to be more acceptable to PSM in some parts of Asia. For example, Korean Broadcasting System (KBS) has introduced them

to “read” local news bulletins³⁶. PTS (Taiwan) also has a 2-D AI presenter called “Handsome P” which is used to host on special occasions or to present quizzes after the news³⁷. While NHK (Japan) has previously used an animé character named “Yomiko” to read the news³⁸, but withdrew her due to programming changes.

However, NHK (Japan), PTS (Taiwan) and SRG SSR (Switzerland) are all working on developing virtual sign-readers because of their commitments to universal access. NHK hopes to use a virtual sign-reader called “Kiki” as an “ambassador” during the DeafOlympics in November 2025³⁹. But at the time of inquiring in January 2025, NHK researchers said that “Kiki” was not yet operational because of several “practical issues,” including translational accuracy. This is not surprising because sign-language generation is a very challenging task, which academic researchers have been trying to solve for over two decades⁴⁰.

³⁵ theguardian.com/tv-and-radio/2023/oct/20/here-is-the-news-you-cant-stop-us-ai-anchor-zae-in-grants-us-an-interview

³⁶ Seo, S. (2025) ‘Performing Publicness: AI and PSMs in South Korea.’ International Communication Association conference, Denver, CO, 12-16 June.

³⁷ youtube.com/watch?v=LJC4uMekmX0

³⁸ nhk.or.jp/strl/english/publica/bt/74/8.html

³⁹ nhk-ep.co.jp/signlanguage/en

⁴⁰ link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10209-021-00823-1

6.3. Synthetic voices

PSM obligations vis-à-vis universal access also motivated four organisations to pilot text-to-speech tools for these purposes. Although some interviewees explained they envisaged synthetic voices having a secondary use: providing 'voice-overs' for clips, or at times when the network was short-staffed (for example, on overnight shifts).

These organisations were ABC (Australia), Suspilne (Ukraine), VRT (Flemish-Belgium), and one other organisation, which chose not to be named in this context. The tools these organisations were piloting included products from the UK-based firm ElevenLabs⁴¹, and Microsoft Cognitive Services.

The main ethical issue raised by PSM involved using cloned human voices which they thought could be deceptive, especially if they cloned the voices of their own journalists, which would also raise questions about copyright. For these reasons, most preferred to use fully synthetic or "robot" voices.

6.4. Challenges: Ethics

The use of AI image generation and editing was frequently mentioned by interviewees in relation to ethical concerns. Most PSM which 'officially' used these tools strictly limited the use of AI image generation and editing, especially in news because of its special relationship to accuracy and truth-telling.

However, organisations varied in their approach: some, like SRG SSR (Switzerland) kept a regularly updated, public-facing site outlining their editorial guidance in detail⁴³. But most offered more detailed editorial guidance internally, as this could be updated more easily.

Interviewees who stressed the need to oversee AI image generation/editing in detail tended to link this to examples of serious mistakes, which had occurred in their own and others' news organisations.

For example, interviewees at ABC (Australia) discussed what appeared to be an incident of algorithmic bias, in which a domestic non-ABC

The exception was NHK (Japan), whose in-house team had developed synthetic voices designed to resemble specific announcers⁴². NHK interviewees believe these are more effective at conveying information accurately, so were used for early morning TV news, for introducing electoral candidates, and for issuing public information messages during emergencies.

In contrast with visual AI avatars, only one PSM, Suspilne (Ukraine), raised concerns about synthetic voices and "deepfakes." In addition, one of the specialised trainers stressed that the use of "deepfake" voices was most likely to be a concern for PSM working in contexts where radio was still the primary medium, including many countries in Sub-Saharan Africa.

TV network had used AI tools to edit a photo of a female politician. The published image sexualised the politician by enlarging her breasts and placing her in a crop top, exposing her midriff⁴⁴.

The ABC interviewee said this informed the organisation's guidance about the need to avoid using AI to alter "material reality", and their efforts to oversee the functions of AI tools, even though this was challenging. For example, they clarified that journalists working in news and other factual content were permitted to use generative "auto-fill" functions to improve the appearance of patchy hedge, but were not permitted to make a crowd of people look larger than it was, which could have more significant political implications⁴⁵.

The interviewee at RNZ (New Zealand) spoke about the ways in which one of their journalists had made an error, which prompted managers to "tighten up the supply chain" of stock images. This involved insisting that third-party image providers provide more detailed metadata,

as journalists could not always spot AI-generated or edited images.

In this case, an audience member had called RNZ to say the network had inadvertently published an AI-generated stock image on its website. The RNZ executive remarked:

"I'm not sure our journalist had ever seen a platypus before... but it could have been a lot more serious."

Despite widespread alarm among PSM senior managers about the potential for AI presenters to embolden 'bad actors' spreading mis- and disinformation, there seems to be a much clearer international consensus here than on other areas of AI-enabled image generation and editing.

Questions for further discussion:

- Should editorial guidance about the use of AI-generated images and AI enabled editing be public or internal?
- How detailed does editorial guidance need to be? For example, should PSM audit AI tools or functions of tools?
- How can PSM make the continual updating of guidance and related training manageable?
- Should PSM avoid using AI tools alleged to have been trained in ways that breach others' copyright?
- How can PSM minimise the risk of synthetic voices from being used to spread mis- and disinformation?
- Given PSMs' shared commitment to universal access, might those working on producing virtual sign-readers be willing to share what they are learning?

Image supplied by RNZ.

⁴¹ elevenlabs.io

⁴² nhk.or.jp/str/english/publica/bt/48/3.html

⁴³ srgssr.ch/en/who-we-are/mission-policy-values-and-strategy/ai-principles

⁴⁴ abc.net.au/news/2024-02-01/georgie-purcell-ai-image-nine-news-apology-digital-ethics/103408440

⁴⁵ See also: abc.net.au/edpols/using-ai-tools-in-abc-content/104367478

7. Emerging uses of AI

When all thirteen PSM were asked what uses of AI they wanted to develop in future, a clear, shared priority emerged: most organisations were keen to develop AI to assist the research carried out by journalists. As Diagram 3 shows, PSM were most interested in exploring the potential use of AI to “detect misinformation trends”, to “analyse big data,” and to “engage in fact or claim checking.”

But relatively few PSM chose to tell us about AI tools they used to support journalists’ research. So, it is hard to tell whether these are rarely used or whether PSM simply chose not to disclose them in this study. The tools that participants did choose to talk about tended to involve data journalism, although some PSM were piloting Retrieval-Augmented Generation, which we will discuss before going on to talk about PSMs’ use of AI in content customisation and repurposing.

Diagram 3: The areas of AI use that PSM said they were most interested in developing

⁴⁶ Journaliststudio.google.com
⁴⁷ wobby.ai
⁴⁸ psm-ap.com
⁴⁹ tech.ebu.ch/events/2024/psmgpt-large-language-models-for-public-service-media

7.1. Data Journalism and Retrieval-Augmented Generation

In terms of data journalism, RTBF (Francophone-Belgium) said it currently used CustomGPT Code Copilot to assist with coding in data journalism. Other participants mentioned their exploration of advanced retrieval methods, which helped them sift through large datasets. For instance, ABC (Australia) was piloting Google Pinpoint and NotebookLM, which are part of Google’s Journalist Studio package⁴⁶.

as a valuable provider of RAG tools. It was launched by a former VRT employee to help journalists “have conversations” with open government data, such as that produced by the intergovernmental World Bank.

Participants were also experimenting with Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), a cutting-edge technique that augments an LLM with the ability to retrieve information from specified, external datasets. A small start-up, Wobby⁴⁷, was named by VRT (Flemish-Belgium)

Meanwhile, interviewees at VRT and ABC (Australia) were impressed with trials of Microsoft Copilot, which enabled journalists to check and cite sources. The paid-for version of Copilot was seen as a relatively “safe environment” by one VRT senior manager, because Microsoft promised that journalists’ searches would not be used to harvest data.

7.2. Challenges: Journalism research, the ‘Big Five’, and LLMs

The provision of AI by the ‘Big Five’ technology companies was much more significant in discussions about emerging forms of journalistic research, so PSMs’ dependence on these providers may increase over time. This is a concern, given that many PSM are already heavily dependent on these companies for content distribution⁴⁸.

systems, using the verified content of participating PSMs. In addition, participants hoped that such LLMs would be less vulnerable to cyberattacks, including prompt injections, and less likely to leak private conversation histories.

It is worth noting that some European PSMs have been trying to develop their own LLMs for use in journalistic research⁴⁹. For example, Yle (Finland) has used this to produce a RAG tool, which it calls “YLEGPT⁵⁰. SR (Sweden) was also piloting a RAG tool produced by EBU, Neo⁵¹, in non-audience-facing contexts. Neo allows journalists to conduct conversational searches of a large database of news content produced by EBU members, translated using its EuroVOX tool⁵².

However, interviewees at SRG SSR (Switzerland) expressed reservations about developing their own LLMs, as they believed this would be highly energy-intensive, so could cause environmental harm⁵³. Moreover, even if PSMs successfully develop their own LLMs, they are still likely to need the foundational models provided by external parties to operate. Therefore, developing in-house LLMs may offer PSMs greater relative autonomy, but it’s unlikely to represent a complete “alternative” to commercial models.

In theory, using in-house RAG tools reduces the risk of “hallucinations” and data bias because these tools are trained and operate within secure

⁵⁰ tech.ebu.ch/publications/presentations/dts2024/yle_gpt
⁵¹ Discussed in this EBU report: ebu.ch/guides/open/report/news-report-2024-trusted-journalism-in-the-age-of-generative-ai
⁵² tech.ebu.ch/eurovox
⁵³ This research interview was conducted prior to the release of DeepSeek’s open-source models, which challenge this belief. reuters.com/technology/artificial-intelligence/what-is-deepseek-why-is-it-disrupting-ai-sector-2025-01-27

7.3. Open-Source Intelligence Tools

Two PSM said that their journalists used specialised Open-Source Intelligence tools to aid their investigative research, when checking facts or claims. VRT (Flemish-Belgium) said their journalists used Google Pinpoint⁵⁴ and GeoSpy⁵⁵ to analyse who was in photographs, as well as when and where they had been taken: describing such uses as growing out of a longstanding commitment to checking facts and claims.

Meanwhile, documentary journalists at Suspilne (Ukraine) said they used facial recognition technology, specifically PimEyes⁵⁶, Findclone⁵⁷, and Search4faces⁵⁸, to identify Russian soldiers whom they allege were involved in war crimes—including the 2022 massacre of civilian volunteers in Bucha⁵⁹. These AI tools use images scraped from online and social media, but two are Russian. So journalists used VPNs to access these sites

7.4. Challenges: The ethics of facial recognition

Yet PSMs' use of facial recognition technology (FRT) raises difficult ethical questions. On one hand, the Global Investigative Journalists' Network has previously argued that journalists' use of FRT enables them to resist authoritarian oppression, enhance accuracy, accountability, and the rule of law⁶⁰.

On the other hand, journalists' use of FRT raises questions about their personal and organisational vulnerability, as well as the possible misidentification of subjects. The use of tools so commonly deployed in espionage and counterespionage also needs to be examined in relation to PSMs' independence from funding governments, especially at a time of digital warfare.

and hide their IP addresses. Investigative journalists estimated that these tools were helpful in identifying suspects in 30% of the cases investigated. This was used alongside more traditional methods, including interviewing witnesses.

Suspilne interviewees stressed they had consulted with the Ukrainian government to ensure that journalists did not break any laws and provided evidence to the Ukrainian police to help with their investigations. However, Suspilne does not have an approval process for these AI tools. So its investigative journalists carry significant personal responsibility: identifying and paying for relevant tools, as well as conducting their own risk assessments.

Given PSMs' democratic mandate, they should consider whether using FRT in investigative research or archival retrieval risks normalising this technology—which is a core feature of authoritarian surveillance. In addition, the willingness of audiences to accept journalists' use of FRT may also vary, even within the same country.

For example, ongoing research into UK attitudes to AI conducted by the Ada Lovelace Institute⁶¹, indicated high levels of support for the use of FRT surveillance within police/security. However, ethnic minorities and people living in Northern Ireland were far more concerned about FRT being used in these contexts. It is possible that PSM already have detailed editorial policies on the use of facial recognition, but these were not included on the documentation we saw.

⁵⁴ journaliststudio.google.com/pinpoint/about

⁵⁵ geospy.ai

⁵⁶ pimeyes.com/en

⁵⁷ findclone.ru

⁵⁸ search4faces.com

⁵⁹ youtube.com/watch?v=LBrbVkhG5wM

⁶⁰ gijn.org/resource/facial-recognition-made-easy

⁶¹ adalovelaceinstitute.org/report/ai-public-good discussed by O'Keefe, E. and Modhvardia, R. (2025). 'AI and Society'. Presentation to BRAID Community Gathering, Manchester, 18 June.

7.5. Repurposing News Content

Despite PSMs' shared enthusiasm for using AI in journalistic research, our survey and interview data suggested that the most rapidly growing use of AI in PSMs actually involved the repurposing of multimedia content for online and social media platforms. Six participants, ABC (Australia), NHK (Japan), PTS (Taiwan), SRG SSR (Switzerland), VRT (Belgium) and another said they already used AI for this, and others said they were "interested" or "very" interested in developing similar uses of AI.

PSM that currently use AI to repurpose content sometimes deployed it to automate or semi-automate a single task. For example, NHK (Japan) uses an in-house tool to automatically create short video summaries of longer news reports for online.

PTS (Taiwan) is developing a similar auto-editing tool in collaboration with a commercial partner to produce video clips for social media. While SRG SSR (Switzerland) uses an in-house tool to locate and extract thumbnail images from video, which interviewees estimated saved journalists 10–15 minutes every time.

Other PSM had invested in developing multi-functional systems. For instance, VRT (Flemish-Belgium) had a "Smart News Assistant", capable of summarising long articles and facilitating

copy/editing and proofreading⁶². The network was also developing or piloting new functions for "Smart News Assistant", including translating wire copy, generating Tik-Tok scripts and WhatsApp messages from news content, and even suggesting news headlines.

Accurate, detailed metadata are necessary to ensure that these AI tools and systems work properly, so the automation of metadata was the subject of considerable research and development work within wealthier PSMs. For example, ABC (Australia) has developed its own Large Language Model (LLM), which was primarily geared towards the production of news metadata.

However, SRG SSR (Switzerland) and NHK (Japan) have been working on integrating facial recognition into metadata⁶³, which begs further ethical discussion (see previous section on "The ethics of facial recognition"). Nevertheless, AI-enabled repurposing of news content tended to be regarded by PSM as uncontroversial given widespread budget cuts and rising costs. All claimed that it did not affect the human-centred creation of the original piece of journalism.

⁶² ebu.ch/video-talks/membersonly/2024/12/showcase-smart-news-assistant-vrt

⁶³ For example: nhk.or.jp/strl/english/open2024/tenji/12/index.html

7.6. Challenges: 'Mission Creep'

Some of the language used to describe repurposing forms of AI appears to make it susceptible to "mission creep." That is, a gradual expansion of the purposes for which AI was implemented over time. For example, AI applications that automated or semi-automated a single task were consistently referred to by participants as "tools," emphasizing human agency and control. We found no instances where these "tools" were used for purposes other than those originally intended.

By contrast, AI-enabled systems with multiple functions tended to be described by managers as "assistants" or "interns", which framed AI's relationship to journalists in anthropomorphised (but subservient) terms. These seemed to gain more new functions over time, some of which were editorial.

But the most striking example of potential "mission creep" involved Microsoft's branding of its tool as a "Copilot", which positions AI as an equal "team mate." It was interesting to note that VRT interviewees said they were considering a "broader structural engagement" with Microsoft Copilot, which they described as a "brainstorm buddy." One VRT participant elaborated on this by saying that, hypothetically, journalists could potentially use Microsoft Copilot to compile the first draft of short news items, provided there was human oversight.

Questions for further discussion:

- Given that PSM have identified using AI in journalistic research as a shared strategic priority, what scope is there for collective dialogue and collaboration? In what ways might collaboration avoid growing dependence on the 'Big Five' technology companies?
- Using AI to identify misinformation is notoriously difficult technically, and sharing details of these techniques carries risks for PSM. Is it possible to take this conversation forward collectively in some way, or must this remain a matter for internal discussion?
- Do PSM have (or need) a shared ethical position on the use of Open-Source Intelligence Tools, especially facial recognition technology, within investigative journalism or content repurposing?
- What kinds of 'mission creep' might PSM wish to guard against?

Image: AI supported text support for the hearing impaired from Swedish Radio

8. Conclusion

We want to start by thanking the PSM that participated in this global research project. We recognise that study participation not only involved senior managers contributing their time and energy, but also trusting us to handle their data responsibly and represent their views faithfully.

The discussions we had with participants about organisational and personal consent made it clear that AI is seen, almost universally, as highly sensitive amongst PSM. In part, this is because of the challenges it poses the distinctiveness of PSM, as well as the complexity of trying to square AI use with PSM values and efficiency objectives.

Many PSM are also experiencing political and commercial pressure, as well as heightened diplomatic sensitivities, and increasing concerns about data privacy and cybersecurity. In such circumstances, it is not surprising that PSM are hesitant to give too much away about their Intellectual Property.

We also recognise that PSM have varying levels of experience with AI. Those with higher organisational incomes tended to have used AI for much longer than those with lower incomes. Indeed, those with low incomes tended not to have developed any AI strategies yet — although some had reason to believe their journalists were using AI 'unofficially' on private devices.

Unofficial AI usage was widely seen by managers and specialist trainers as posing significant risks regarding cybersecurity and data privacy. Although the process of adopting AI applications 'officially' could also expose some PSM to risks: exposing them to politicisation via governing and governmental bodies, and potentially creating obvious targets for cybercrime.

Support from, and knowledge exchange between, PSM was seen as vital in helping them engage with AI responsibly, but Europe continues to be the main hub for collective discussion and productisation.

PSMs' ability to engage effectively in regional and cross-regional networks also varied widely because

of their income. High-income and medium-income PSM were more able to talk to one another via formal associations, informal networks and bilateral relationships. Other regional meetings such as those between PSM in Oceania are becoming more frequent, helping to facilitate intra- and cross-regional dialogue.

However, other low and medium-income PSM appear to have been less frequently included in these exchanges, including those in politically sensitive countries in Africa (i.e., South Africa), Asia (i.e., Taiwan), and the far East of Europe (i.e., Moldova, Ukraine), as well as PSM in countries likely to experience the worst effects of climate change (i.e., Jamaica). PMA's support for a regional meeting for Southern African PSM, hosted by SABC in 2024, and the cross-regional conference hosted by PTS (Taiwan) in 2024 may have offset some of these difficulties.

Yet three key problems remain. These are: the lack of comparable regional PSM-focussed hubs to EBU that are able to invest significant resources into responsible AI, poorer PSMs' difficulties in finding the time and energy to engage in these conversations, and richer PSMs' lack of understanding of the limitations faced by less well-resourced peers. Thus, PSM with different, and potentially more challenging, perspectives risk becoming marginalised within PSMs' collective conversations about responsible AI.

Nevertheless, the PSM that said they used AI 'officially' tended to do so in similar, human-centred ways. The most common involved using speech-to-text tools to transcribe content or create closed captions, almost all of which were checked manually. Accurate transcription is also the foundation for AI translation and developing this area was of great interest to multilingual PSM. However, PSM with obligations to serve the speakers of minority and Indigenous languages faced particularly difficult ethical, political, financial and technical challenges, which deserve greater attention.

The second most common use of AI was image-editing, although this tended to be the area that PSM raised the most serious ethical concerns, given the prevalence of 'fake news'. Interestingly, attitudes to AI presenters and synthetic voices varied more significantly between PSM, with East Asian participants tending to be more comfortable with limited use of the former, and participants in hostile (and potentially, radio-dependent environments) tending to express more caution regarding the latter.

The most rapidly emerging use of AI amongst PSM seemed to be content repurposing. Unlike other uses of AI this tended to be treated as largely uncontroversial since it did not affect the human creation of the original piece of journalism. While such uses of AI potentially offer PSM significant efficiencies, they need to be aware of the propensity of AI systems to develop unexamined forms of 'mission creep' into editorial tasks, including the generation of headlines and even 'first drafts' of articles. This risk appears to be increased when AI is imagined in anthropomorphic terms, especially when these position AI as an equal team-mate or Copilot.

Although PSM said they were most interested in developing the use of AI in journalistic research, relatively few PSM told us about this. This could be because PSM are largely interested in the use of AI to identify mis- and disinformation, and such uses are particularly difficult to discuss in public. Those PSM that did choose to tell us about these applications were either piloting cutting-edge tools (such as RAG) or else using OSINT tools, such as facial recognition technology.

In our opinion, the latter deserves far more ethical discussion, given the origins of such tools, and the widespread usage of facial recognition technology in population surveillance within authoritarian countries.

Finally, it was surprising to see that PSMs' dependence on the AI tools provided by the 'Big Five' technology companies was less pronounced than expected, although there was evidence that they provided vital infrastructure. In addition, PSM were still heavily dependent on commercial AI products, which makes it more difficult for them to be transparent with audiences, challenges their claims regarding operational independence, and could potentially expose them to commercial and political influence.

However, despite the pressure on PSM to create complete 'alternatives' to commercial AI⁶⁴, this is not always possible because of the limited number of foundational models. Generating greater relative independence from commercial AI also takes specialist expertise and financial resources that most PSM simply do not have.

⁶⁴ informationdemocracy.org/artificial-intelligence

9. Appendix

The AI tools cited by PSM that 'officially' use AI in journalism production.

Category	How Provided	AI company and product	How many organisations cited tool	Data used	Function/s described by participants	Limitations described by participants
Audience analysis	External	Talkwalker	1	Online news data	Visualises hot topics of interest to audience; gauges responses to news output	
Captions	External	GoodTape	1	Video	Automated captions	Accuracy in Chinese needs improvement
Captions/ Transcription	In-house	N/a	1	Audio	Automated captions and transcription	On-premises infrastructure within the organisation
Copy-editing/Proof-reading	External	Grammarly	1	Text	Online written articles, broadcast scripts	Subscription costly and free version has limited writing suggestions
Digital product development	External	Microsoft GitHub Copilot	1	Code, prompt	Development of digital products	
Headline optimisation	External	Chartbeat	1	News article	Generates headline suggestions likely to be popular with audience	Rarely and sporadically used by 2 members of staff only
Image generation/editing	External	Adobe (Photoshop)	3	Prompt	-General editing	
Image generation/editing	External	Adobe (Firefly)	3	Artwork and prompt	-Generates images to promote programmes on social media -General editing	Used in conjunction with Adobe Suite

					-Generates graphics for online journalism and social media -Audio-visual illustration of stories or social media promotion of content	Only used for marginal decorative elements, guidelines do not permit use for illustrating web articles. Exceptions occasionally made on case-by-case basis, e.g., to illustrate video narration with non-photorealistic images.
Image generation/editing	External	Canva	1	Artwork/prompt	Generates graphics for social media posts	Limited templates, design options
Image generation/editing	External	OpenAI Dall-E	1	Prompt	Story illustration or social media promotion of content	Only used for marginal decorative elements, guidelines do not permit use for illustrating web articles. Exceptions occasionally made on case-by-case basis, e.g., to illustrate video narration with non-photorealistic images.
Image generation	In house		1	Graphics	Creates virtual host	Not 3D
Image generation	External	Midjourney	2	Prompt	-audiovisual illustration of stories, content promotion on social media	- Only used for marginal decorative elements, guidelines do not permit use for illustrating web articles. Exceptions occasionally made on case-by-case basis, e.g., to illustrate video narration with non-photorealistic images.
Image thumbnail extraction	Hybrid – collaboration with consultant	-	1	Video +prompt	Selects most appropriate image based on given criteria	-No subscription for staff, so used at own expense
Multifunction Proposes topic metadata *In development: Research functions	In-house	N/a	1	News text	Currently content customisation	Limited to digital text, broader metadata options needed

Multifunction Copy editing/Proof-reading Summarisation Automated generation of WhatsApp messages *In development: Title suggestion Translation Generate TikTok scripts	In-house	N/a	1	Published articles	Currently journalistic research, reversioning, pilot extending functionality to aid efficiency	Makes errors with larger articles Scalability Workflow integration
Multifunction Transcription Suggests video clips	Hybrid- details not given	Based on AWSBedrock, Anthropic Claude LLM AWS/Transcribe	1	Video + transcription or image searches	Transcribes video and proposes clips from longer pieces using transcription or image search	Struggles with some contexts (eg. sports, press conferences)
Multifunction Analysing data, time filter, person detection, locations, organisations, plus transcription, audio search, text recognition in images	External	Google PinPoint	1	Text	Investigative journalism	Sometimes too eager to link people and locations. Can only transcribe one language per file.
Research/Content generation	External	OpenAI ChatGPT	1	Prompt	Online and broadcast coverage of ChatGPT only	Privacy and Security concerns
Research	External	OpenAI ChatGPT and Microsoft Bing (integrated tool)	1	Prompt	Assisted searches	
Research (Data journalism)	External	Wobby	1	Government Open Datasets	Enables conversations with big datasets for investigative journalism	Background in data journalism still necessary to interpret results. Some hallucinations.
Research (Data journalism)	External	OpenAI Custom GPT Code Copilot	1	Prompt	Helps journalist write code for data journalism	Requires expertise in coding
Research (Investigative)	External	Findclone	1	Image	Assists person-identification	Russian tool requires VPN, combined with other methods No subscription for staff, so used at own risk/expense

Research (Investigative)	External	EMEARobotics PimEyes	1	Image	Assists person-identification	Used in combination with other methods. No subscription for staff, so used at own risk/expense
Research (Investigative)	External	Search4Faces	1	Image	Assists person-identification	Russian tool, requires VPN, combined with other methods. No subscription for staff, so used at own risk/expense
Research (Fact/claim checking)	External	Google Reverse image search	1	Image	Find image published on internet based on image uploaded	
Research (Fact/claim checking)	External	Graylark Technologies GeospyPro	1	Image	Describes location where picture taken	Accuracy limited, esp. if indoors
Sound optimisation	In-house		1	Audio	Increase audibility, esp. in-car listeners	
Synthetic voices	External	ElevenLabs	2	Audio/Video	-Clones voice for use in news, sport, entertainment -Breaking news when not enough staff on shift; when don't have enough voices to translate speeches; voices online articles for accessibility	-Variable quality, e.g. poor expression/too fast/accents/pronunciation -Partially free, only have one subscription. Initially piloted using presenters' voices but have decided to use wholly synthetic
Synthetic voices	In-house	N/a	1	Audio of presenter reading + Text	Clones voice for use in TV news, political broadcasts, weather forecast and more.	Limited to use in script-reading style speech
Transcription	In-house	N/a	1		Accessibility, metadata generation	
Transcription	External	cSubtitle Pro	1	Text	Used internally to produce video captions. Distinguishes three languages/dialects: Taiwanese Mandarin, Chinese Mandarin, and Hong Kong Cantonese	Transcription is not sufficiently accurate to fully automate captions. Manual checks and corrections need to be carried out by journalists first
Transcription	External	OtterAI	1	Audio	Transcribes radio interviews/reports	Accuracy poor, difficulty coping with dialect
Transcription	External	Trint	1	Audio/video	Summarisation for research purposes	Scalability- use a different tool for other purposes

Transcription	External	Sonix	2	Audio/video	-Transcribes Chinese and English -General transcription	-Real-time accuracy needs improving -SaaS product so not used with highly confidential content
Transcription	External	Various -not named	1	Audio	Radio journalism	Accuracy too poor for publication Not all tools used by journalists satisfy organisational requirements re: contracts/data security.
Transcription	Hybrid- some customisation	AWS/Transcribe but switching to Google (DeepMind)	1	Audio/video	Generic journalism	Varying quality of transcription per language
Transcription	Hybrid- customised internal interface	Systran's FasterWhisper Uses OpenAI Whisper + a fast inference engine. CTranslate2	1	Audio, video, YouTube links	Generic news.	Scalability limited use.
Transcription	Hybrid- customised internal interface	-	1	Audio	All- Recognises local dialects and voices speaking in German, French, Italian, Romansh (more for international service)	Quality/Accuracy - must be reviewed. Can only cope with monolingual transcription, cannot switch between languages
Translation	Hybrid - industry collaboration	Microsoft	1	Published news	Radio journalism. Uses own transcription tool in combination with Microsoft Copilot to translate, for internal use only.	
Translation	Collaboration	EBU EuroVOX	1	Published news	Translation	
Translation	External	-	1	Any	Integrated into journalistic workflows	Accuracy/Quality, needs to be reviewed
Video editing	In house	N/a	1	News video	Auto-edits longer video reports into summaries for online news.	Limited to structured news segments, as it relies on the structure of news item

'Independence,'
'Impartiality,'
'Accountability,'
'Transparency,'
'Universality,'
Trust